

Nira variety - a susceptible host for mass rearing rice thrips *Srenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall)

E. B. Medina and R. C. Saxena, Entomology Department, IIRRI

Peak infestation of rice by thrips occurs during late Jul-Oct and Jan-early Apr in the Philippines. For a continuous supply of thrips to screen rice germplasm for resistance and for associated basic studies, suitable rice varieties are needed for thrips mass rearing. We evaluated thrips population growth on varieties Nira, Dawn, TN1, Pankhari 203, IR42, TKM6, Rexoro, and Kinanda (all considered susceptible) and Dahanala 2220 (resistant).

Three-week-old seedlings of each variety grown in pots (15-cm-diam) at 5 seedlings/pot were infested with 5 pairs of male and female thrips and covered with snug-fitting mylar cages, with 5 replications/entry. Eggs, larvae, prepupae, pupae, and adults on each plant were counted 14 d after infestation (DI).

Increase in thrips population was significantly higher on Nira; Dahanala 2220 had the lowest population (see table). The suitability of Nira for thrips mass rearing was further evaluated by exposing to natural thrips infestation potted Nira plants at 15, 20, 30, 40, and 50 d after transplanting. Regardless of plant age, no significant differences in thrips establishment were observed. Even older Nira plants could be used to maintain a thriving thrips culture year-round. □

Populations of thrips *S. biformis* on different rice varieties.^a IIRRI, 1986.

Variety	IIRRI acc. no.	Thrips ^b (no.) at 14 DI
Nira	6309	56 a
Dawn	02029	41 b
TN1	105	37 bc
Pankhari 203	5999	33 bcd
IR42	36959	28 bcd
TKM6	237	24 cd
Rexoro	143	23 cd
Kinanda	3882	18 d
Dahanala 2220	50730	0.60 e

^a Av of 5 replications. ^b From 25 pairs of males and females. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Effect of insecticide treatment at different rice crop stages on carry-over of yellow stem borer (YSB)

H.V. Pandya, A.H. Shah, and M.S. Purohit, Entomology Department, N.M. College of Agriculture, Gujarat Agricultural University, Navsari Campus, Navsari 396450, Gujarat, India

YSB larvae hibernating in rice stubbles can carry over infestation if continuous cropping is practiced. We studied the effect of insecticides applied at various crop growth stages on the intensity of hibernating larvae. The 2-season

Effect of insecticides applied at different crop stages on YSB carry-over. Navsari, India, 1986 summer and wet season.

Treatment ^a	Hibernating larvae (no.)/10 stubbles per plot		
	1986 summer	1986 wet season	Pooled
Maximum protection	4.0	2.2	3.1
Maximum protection except in seedbed	4.8	3.2	4.0
Maximum protection except at vegetative stage	4.8	3.2	4.0
Maximum protection except at reproductive stage	5.3	4.0	4.6
Maximum protection except at ripening stage	4.4	2.9	3.6
Seedbed protection only	9.0	6.8	7.9
Vegetative stage protection only	7.8	5.8	6.8
Reproductive stage protection only	5.3	3.6	4.4
Ripening stage protection only	6.8	4.8	5.8
Control (no protection)	9.6	7.8	8.7
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.3	0.3

^a Maximum protection = seedbed protection: carbofuran 3 G at 0.5 kg ai/ha 5 d before transplanting; vegetative stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at 5 and 25 d after transplanting (DT), application of carbofuran 3 G at 1.0 kg ai/ha at 15 DT, and foliar spray of fenitrothion 50 EC at 0.05% at 35 DT; reproductive stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at panicle initiation and flowering; ripening stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at soft dough stage.

Effect of some insecticide formulations against newly emerged yellow stem borer (YSB) larvae

H.V. Pandya, A.H. Shah, and M.S. Purohit, Entomology Department, N.M. College of Agriculture, Gujarat Agricultural University, Navsari Campus, Navsari 396450, Gujarat, India

We conducted a laboratory experiment to determine the efficacy of some insecticide formulations against newly emerged larvae of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas*. Aqueous 0.04%

experiment with 10 treatments was in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Larval population after harvest was determined by splitting 10 randomly selected stubbles from each treatment plot and counting the larvae found.

The number of hibernating larvae was lowest with the maximum protection treatment, followed by maximum protection except during ripening (see table). Other treatments had comparatively higher numbers of hibernating larvae. □

Effect of some insecticide formulations against newly emerged YSB larvae. Navsari, India.

Treatment	Formulation	Larval mortality ^a (%)
Monocrotophos	36 WSC	68.9
Fenitrothion	50 EC	65.9
Cypermethrin	25 EC	60.1
Carbaryl	50 WP	52.1
Chlorpyrifos	20 EC	63.1
Diazinon	20 EC	39.7
Methyl parathion	50 EC	61.6
Water	-	12.6
No treatment	-	8.4
CD (0.05)		1.4

^a Av of 3 replications. Data converted to angular values.